

BM-5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR

A Reflective Critique Report

by:

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BM 5102 Organizational Behavior is one of the core modules for Master of Management. At the beginning of the semester, students are informed on the workloads the module carries and the lecturer's expectation for her students to cope with the workloads throughout the semester. The module consists of two major assignments namely; a case study group work project and Individual Analysis Paper. Hence, the assignments further breakdown into several assignments and datelines. Concerning COVID-19 restriction and guidelines from the university, lecturers are required to conduct their teaching online and I believed that examination should be eliminated as part of the module's requirement. As a result, the basis of the modules is a hundred percent coursework. Having said that, the transition of full coursework might be heavy for some students, especially to the returning students. Even more, the use of canvas might be a bit unfamiliar to some students particularly, for non UBD students and returning students who graduated for more than 2 years where canvas played less part in the learning system at that time. The number of new inputs on how to prepare ourselves for online learning and coursework basis might be overwhelming. The time of myself to adapt to the environment are longer than I ever expected. While the lack of physical interaction between the lecturer and other colleagues makes it harder as I am not able to make a connection.

Moreover, as someone who is not from a business degree background, I need time and effort to understand and digest new information especially on the theoretical approach and the research methods and analytical tools that I have never learn before such as systematic literature review, AEIOU, so on and so forth. In the nutshell, most of the new techniques and methods I could learn from none other but in this module. I esteem that, the lecturer has used diverse teaching methods to help the students to explore themselves as a 'researcher' and not as a student. I believed that it will be useful for students in their future career, where this module allow us not only we could learn on how to sharpen our research skills but also through this modules, we could be able to understand people's as an individual as well as in a group setting. Theories on motivations per se explained how certain elements could motivate an individual and affect their overall performances in the workplace.

For instance, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs described that an individual needs psychological, security, love, esteem, and, self-actualization which allows the manager to give fair discernment to their subordinates (Wied & Suchowsky, 1954). Similarly, intrinsic and extrinsic motivators have given insights for managers on what to expect from their employees. In relation to that, these theories could be helpful to identify the reflection of people's outcomes and efforts in particular tasks assigned to them. Given that, as a student we need to motivations to cope the challenges and for the sake of our mental health, positive thinking is needed.

In contrast, like all of the other core modules that I took this semester and offered a hundred percent coursework, these module workloads are the heaviest among all. Consequently, I consumed more time and, effort in this module. Because the major assignments are classified into sub-assignments, more time is required to meet the datelines. In that respect, it leads to demotivation and lack of interest as the same topics are repeatedly researching throughout the semester. This could be related to McGregor's theory X where the authors asserted that lack of motivation has caused to disliking the task and hence, decrease the productivity (Griffin, 2015). However, building up encouragement and realization of the responsibility as a postgraduate student has pushed me to complete the work in time. Positively, it could indirectly train us to be

prepared in multitasking and managed our time efficiently which is required when we enter the working environment.

Likewise, in this module, students are exposed to a peer review system, particularly for Individual Analysis Paper. According to Elsevier (n.d.), peer review is where we are supposed to review and give an evaluation of the work with the same frequency as we are and it is believed will help to improve the quality of academic writing. It further stated that, although that type of method is critically disapproved, in some manner it is the effective way of research method for academic purposes. Nevertheless, from the student's perspective, it might be unnecessary because it is reviewed by students, not professional (lecturer). From reading several peers' papers, multiple formats and systems are used and implemented in the same task. The students' might be wonder if the critique is relevant and up to academic standards. As a result, it could enhance confusion and doubt the work that has been submitted. It is, however, solely the students' judgemental skills that need to be improve and by any means correlated with the personality traits and cognitive ability that could have differed from one another.

Equivalently, this module has taught the importance of understanding the personality traits and one that is vastly used by the business organization is personality traits developed by Myers Briggs (MBTI). The indicators are based on a combination of six basic elements; sensing-intuition, thinking-feeling, and, judging-perceiving which are then classified into extraversion or introversion ("The Myers & Briggs Foundation - MBTI® Basics", n.d.). Besides, O'Brien et al. (1998) deduced the concepts of learning styles that were categorized into four stages; personality, the process of information, social interaction, and pedagogy methods. As personality is correlated with the MBTI, the processing information of an individual might differ from the other. Some might be able to adapt well and vice versa. Henceforth, cognitive ability is shown to have contributed to the highest potential when it comes to digesting new information (O'Brien et al., 1998). While pedagogy methods of teaching constitute the student's interest in particular modules, lack of social interaction during online learning distracts students from understanding the modules better. Therefore, the lecturer's initiative to turn the lecture into traditional physical classes and actively facilitating the students during consultation hours allows us to interact more and asked questions on further inquiries.

The case study assignment evolved with working in a group helps a social interaction despite the online base learning. Ideally, it offered social interaction and sharing of pieces of knowledge and ideas when working in a group setting. Furthermore, diverse group member facilitates the expansion of knowledge and could improve the effort and performance especially when complex tasks are given (Zajonc as cited in Baumeister et al., 2016) However, for a lot of time, constraints such other commitment and time availability, working in a group caused the work produce not on what we have expected. Some might put more effort and contribution to the task than the other. Thus, as a member of the group, we should understand an individual's situation or difficulty that they have encountered. By any means, put negative thoughts aside. As a result, discussion and interaction can make through Whatsapp and Google Docs. Per contra, in the era of the industrial revolution, 4.0 students are expected to fully maximize the advantages of technology so that students as new generation and representative of Brunei youth can compete with the global market.

Initially, both assignments (case study and individual analysis paper) were instructed to write based on the primary data. Primary data involves distributing questionnaires and conducting interviews. As the assignments required a breakdown of sub-assignments, the process of developing the research topic, constructing the skeleton plans, pilot study and, research design has been done from the beginning of the semester and it continuously progressing until the final submission at the end of the semester. Unfortunately, due to faculty change of rules on ethics, the primary research is not the possible option, unless those who got approval upon. As a result, I assumed most students have to change their research methods last minute. Luckily, the lecturer provides us with alternatives such as systematic literature reviews or projects and further giving us guidelines on how to construct secondary data research. Hence, the lecturer also gave flexibility by extending the submission, albeit, we need to start from the beginning as I have to change the main focus of the topic.

As part of Master of Management core subject, this module has taught me the essentiality of management as a whole from how to manage time efficiently despite needs to chasing with the datelines most of the times (with the other modules as well), taught us on how to understand an individual and teamwork from the concepts and theories that have been offered. Most importantly, as far as I am concerned, through organizational behavior students can practice themselves and as a pre-real-check before actually ready to face employment. The highest unemployment rate Brunei has to face today is agonizing to both the country and the future of the youths. Thorough research and investigation on the focal reason for the issues need to be identified in order the solve the problem. Ironically, most of the unemployed are youths and most of them are youth with education background, compromises from 'O' level graduates to highest educational achievements (Undergraduate, Post-graduate, and Ph.D. per se). Having said that, employers' criteria in selecting their potential employees are no longer solely on educational background, the candidates need to have 'added value' in order to meet the competitive advantages in the workplace. That could be justified by their job experiences and active participation in social organizations. Besides that, unsolved (yet) issued of unemployment could cause by the job seeker's expectation which is found to be a discrepancy to the accessibility of the labor-market (Musa & Idris, 2020). Thus, youths' mindset of employment in Brunei needs to change. Cheong & Lawrey's report (as cited in Musa & Idris, 2020) emphasized on attitudes of the youth and low explorative driven leads to the unemployment remain unsolved. Youths preferred job that required clerical skills compared to manual labor (Musa & Idris, 2020). In spite of that, in my point of view, the education systems in Brunei need to be review. For instance, most of the major universities are based on theoretical learning and lack technical teachings. This could represent student aspirations towards their future career. Moreover, most profit-driven organizations acquired fresh graduates to have at least a minimum of three or more working experiences that perhaps, enhance the probability of the unemployment rate in Brunei. I assumed that, apart from salary stability, bonuses and, job security that government sectors are ready to offer, majorities of sectors in the government do not require minimum working experience, at least on the first-hand job advertisement publish on PSC recruitment website. This is, withal becomes an ideal opportunity for inexperienced job seekers'.

Although, implementation of agenda to combat or the least, minimize the rate of unemployment might be difficult than it has been said. The problem remains a nightmare to the final year (nearly) graduates students. In this module, perhaps, students can plan their strategies efficiently (for the sake of future careers) by taking into account the possibility that may occur.

Hence, mastering the concepts learned in Management course into every aspect of life could assist the student in better decision making. In addition to that, the concept of Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunity, and Threats (SWOT) bring lights and guidelines to the students on what should be done and what should not be done for their life. It is a beneficial strategy to achieve the goals, particularly career-wise. Henceforth, the module taught on the employer expectations towards their future employees that may not be aware by fresh graduate students with no working experiences and related-background to assist them to act during the interviews. This had developed self-awareness on professionalism in the business industry and how to succeed in a career.

To conclude, reflective reports act as a reminder and revision for the students at the end of the semester and, a form for them to recognize their strengths and weaknesses on particular tasks given. It assists us in developing critical thinking and assumption, while able to evaluate freely on certain areas that may not be satisfying and unnecessary. Moreover, it allows us to reflect on the actions and mistakes that we made, whether consciously or not. Additionally, not only it gives advantages to the students but it may also benefit lecturers' to enhance their form of delivering knowledge in the future. Thus, a reflective essay will notify the lecturer of the students' point of view and from there, they will able to improve their teaching methods.

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